

ON PARADIGMATIC AND SYNTAGMATIC RELATIONS

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Abstract. *In this article paradigmatic and syntagmatic relations are studied in different aspects. Information about the nature of paradigmatic and syntagmatic relations is also given. It has been shown that paradigmatic relations allow choosing the necessary unit when using language, as well as forming forms and words by analogy. In syntagmatic relationships, phenomena such as the formation of a ribbon or chain from elements of the same order of a certain length, side by side, one after the other, are scientifically based.*

Keywords: *paradigmatic relations, syntagmatic relations, speech chain, phoneme, morpheme, horizontal, vertical, morph, word forms, sentence, paradigm, syntagma.*

Paradigmatic relationships are relationships that unite language units into groups and categories. Paradigmatic relations, for example, the consonant system, the declension system, are based on the synonymous line. When using language, paradigmatic relations allow to choose the necessary unit, as well as to form forms and words by analogy.

Syntagmatic relations can be defined as compatibility relations of elements of the same level in the speech chain, that is, phoneme with phoneme, morpheme with morpheme, etc.

In a syntagmatic relationship, two or more units are equally connected in a sequence. Ferdinand de Saussure compares a syntagmatic relation to a horizontal column in a given relation to the straight line it supports.

In syntagmatic relationships, one content together with another content, side by side, one after the other, forms a ribbon, a chain of uniform elements of a certain length. For example:

K-i-t-o-b (by the phonetic-phonological method);

Qa-lam, daf-tar (by the morphological method);

Kitob-xon, gul-chi (by the method of word formation);

Katta ko'cha, toza havo (by the lexical method);

Qiziq hikoya (by the syntactic method).

In paradigmatic relations, relations of functional identity of language units, i.e. a paradigm unites a set of language units that are similar in one of the contrasts according to other criteria. Paradigmatic determines to which group of the grammatical category one or another language unit belongs by comparing it with similar ones.

In paradigmatic relations, a unit in the language, such as morph and morpheme, the same word forms, the same sentence forms, occurs in the relationship between different forms. Different grammatical meanings of the same unit are revealed in paradigmatic relations of word forms or syntactic devices. For example, in the agreement paradigm of the noun, different meanings of its forms (book, book, to book); like the conjugation system of the verb.

A paradigm is a relationship between units that can replace each other in the same situation. For example, Red apple (yellow, green) and so on. In this example, yellow and green are reduced to one paradigmatic row.

One of the two aspects of the systematic study of the language is to determine the paradigmatic and syntagmatic relations between the elements or units of the language.

Syntagmatic relations unite language units in a simultaneous sequence. In syntagmatic relations, words are constructed as a set of morphemes and syllables, phrases, clauses, and complex syntactic devices. In language use, syntagmatic relations allow the simultaneous use of two or more units of language.

Paradigmatic relations are horizontal, and syntagmatic relations are distinguished by their location in a vertical row.

The scientific idea of the theoretical scientist Ferdinand de Saussure (1857-1913) is based on the fact that language is a multifaceted phenomenon, full of complex contradictions.

F. de Saussure says that the object of study of linguistics should be speech activity. At the same time, F. de Saussure proved for the first time that speech activity is a whole consisting of language and speech. Therefore, linguistics should study language and speech along with speech activity. F. de Saussure made an absolute distinction between language and speech, and emphasized that they are different phenomena [1.17].

The difference between paradigmatic and syntagmatic relations is associated with the name of Ferdinand Saussure. According to Saussure, the basis of the syntagmatic relationship is the linear nature of the language, which does not allow two elements to be pronounced at the same time. These elements, lined up one after the other in the flow of speech, form compounds called syntagms. This concept applies not only to words, but also to word combinations, complex units of any length (compound words, artificial words, sentences). A phrase is significant only if it contrasts with what precedes it, or what follows it, or both.

A syntagma is an intonation-semantic unit that expresses one concept in a certain context and situation and may consist of a word, a phrase, or a whole sentence.

Syntagmatics includes linguistic rules for the compatibility of language units of one level and their implementation in speech.

The difference between syntagmatics and paradigmatics can be explained by the following example. On the one hand, the form of the word book reminds of other forms of the given word (book, my book, from the book, etc.) and semantically close words (to read, to study, to read). The named forms of the word - the book are combined into a certain type of classification and paradigm. The word "book" and nouns close to it in terms of meaning form a synonymous group built on the basis of paradigmatic relations of lexical meanings.

On the other hand, the word book can be combined with verbs, adjectives and nouns: an interesting book; to read a book; art book etc. The above expressions reveal the form and semantic relations of words built on the basis of syntagmatic relations.

The correspondence of words to each other, that is, their linear arrangement, is a syntagmatic relationship.

Grammatical units of the language form relationships by entering into certain relations with each other. These relationships are of two types: the first is that successive units are connected in a chain, that is, linear relationships; the second is unit relations, that is, non-linear relations, which represent systematic changes of one unit.

Special methods of syntagmatic analysis are developed to determine syntagmatic relations. According to Saussure, they consist of methods of distinguishing linguistic sequences and determining their composition, as well as special methods of determining the influence of one unit on another or their interaction, which is especially evident in phonology and morphology.

A syntagmatic relation consists of two or more members of the relation, which are equally present in the real sequence. Ferdinand de Saussure compares a syntagmatic relation to a rectilinear column, which is a certain relation based on the rule he supports.

Linear relations are called syntagmatic, non-linear relations are called paradigmatic relations. In other words, important parts of units are included in syntagmatic relations - stems and affixes, words, etc. Syntagmatic relations are manifested between words and word forms, between word combinations, in the process of forming a phrase, in the structure of a sentence. At the same time, several units can enter syntagmatic relations. On the basis of these relationships, from words, a complex syntactic device and an extended text take place.

Ferdinand de Saussure also believed that syntagm belongs to language and not to speech. The language contains ready-made expressions, in which custom forbids any change, although the important parts can be distinguished. The nature of these expressions when used in speech depends on the specific features of their meaning or syntax.

Language units are in direct relationship with each other and form a whole system depending on each other. F. de Saussure noted the following about this: "The interaction of language units with the weight of their content develops in two directions that form separate lines. Contrasting these directions allows us to learn more about the nature of each of them. They require two forms of our mental activity, on which the functioning and existence of language depends [2.155]".

It can be seen that F. de Saussure refers here to the paradigmatic and syntagmatic relations of the units of the language system. However, it should also be said that the paradigmatic relation should not be understood as referring to language and the syntagmatic relation to speech. Both of them occur in the material of language units.

The scientist connected such types of syntagms built on the basis of certain rules to the language. Such types exist only if the language has enough copies of them registered.

However, Saussure came to the conclusion that syntagmatically it is really difficult to choose whether one or another syntagm can be related to speech or language. This is because the boundary between the fact of language and the fact of speech, which depends on individual freedom, is blurred. After all, both factors could have been involved in the creation of the syntagma, and in this case, it is impossible to determine.

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